

Human Body Communication: Channel Characterization Issues

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HUMAN Body Communication (HBC) is a promising wireless technology that uses the human body tissues as a signal propagation medium. In HBC the information signal is coupled to the body through an electrostatic or magnetostatic field via electrodes, and is captured in another part of the body using similar electrodes. HBC has a lower power consumption than conventional radio frequency (RF) approaches, because it operates at lower frequencies, usually between 0.1 MHz and 100 MHz, avoiding the body shadowing effects, complex and power hungry RF circuits and antennas. In addition, the signal is mainly confined to the human body, guaranteeing high data communication security and high efficiency in the network utilization. Designs have already been shown [1] to achieve energy efficiency of pJ/bit and power of micro-Watts, paving the way for autonomous, energy harvested powered devices. With these characteristics, HBC helps to reduce the battery volume and consequently the size and the weight of wearable devices, such as watches, earphones, glasses, shoes or clothes. Overall, HBC presents itself as an interesting alternative to

implement Body Sensor Networks (BSN) or Body Area Networks (BAN), especially since it is supported by the IEEE standard 802.15.6 for short-range, low-power and highly reliable wireless communication systems for use in close proximity to, or within, the human body [2].

Currently, three methods for coupling the HBC signals to the body have been proposed: 1) Galvanic coupling; 2) Capacitive coupling; and 3) Magnetic coupling. In the galvanic coupling HBC approach (GHBC), as shown in Fig.1(a), the signal is applied differentially using two transmitter (TX) electrodes in contact with the skin. The stimulated currents are captured using a similar pair of electrodes (also in contact with the skin) in the receiver (RX). This electrode configuration confines the signal within the body, making this method independent of the environment and suitable for implantable devices. However, it has been shown that it only works acceptably with short distances (~ 15 cm) between the transmitter and the receiver and at frequencies below 1 MHz, limiting the data transmission rate [3].

Fig. 1(b) shows the Capacitive coupling HBC (CHBC). In this technique both TX and RX signal electrodes are attached to the skin while the

Fig.1 . Coupling Methods for HBC. (a) Galvanic Coupling (b) Capacitive Coupling (c) Magnetic Coupling.

corresponding ground electrodes are kept floating. Using this electrode configuration an electric field is stimulated in the body, creating a signal path through the human body and a return path through the surrounding environment (e.g. air). The existence of the external ground path means that the capacitive technique is sensitive to the environmental interference. Nevertheless, it provides a higher gain and frequency operation range (up to 100 MHz), in comparison with the GHBC, enabling higher data transmission rates and long distances between TX and RX (~150 cm) [4].

In the Magnetically-coupled HBC (MHBC) the magnetic quasi-static field carries data signals from the TX to the RX, instead of the electrical quasi-static field used in the GHBC and CHBC approaches. MHBC uses a coil to induce a current in the human body, which can be sensed using two RX electrodes that closes the current loop through the body, as shown in Fig. 1(c). As the capacitive coupling, the magnetic coupling approach presents relative long distances of transmission (~120 cm), but in this case, the effects of the environment are minimized [5].

Characterization of the HBC channel is essential for developing models that can aid the design of transceivers to achieve higher data rates and low power consumption for BANs/WBANs. However, finding a proper procedure and measurement setup for characterizing the HBC channel while keeping the signal integrity is a very challenging task, since measurement equipment modifies the channel return path and introduces parasitic effects, influencing the measurement results [3], [4], [6], leading to wrong attenuation levels and frequency profile predictions.

A comparative among GHBC, CHBC and MHBC remarking their principal characteristics for performance evaluation is shown in table I.

TABLE I
PERFORMANCES AND METRICS COMPARISON FOR HBC TECHNIQUES

Characteristic	HBC coupling technique		
	Galvanic	Capacitive	Magnetic
Channel	intrabody	Intrinsic and extrinsic	Intrabody
Contact with the electrodes	All electrodes Contacted with the body	Signal electrodes contacted with the body and ground electrode floating	Contactless
Influence of parasitic paths	Low	High	Low
Instrumentation commonly used for channel characterization	Signal generator and spectrum analyzer	Vector Network Analyzer	Signal generator and spectrum analyzer
Application	Implantable and wearable	wearable	Implantable and wearable
Bit rate	< 1MHz	1–100 MHz	<20 MHz
Communication distance	< 25 cm	< 150 cm	< 120 cm

In the next section, the influence of the measurement equipment, in the experimental characterization of the HBC channel is discussed.

Fig.2. Experimental setup using VNA for HBC channel characterization by. (a) Galvanic technique and (b) Capacitive technique.

Measurement Setups for HBC Channel Characterization

Different measurement devices such as signal generators, spectrum and network analyzers, oscilloscopes and battery-powered transceivers are usually employed to measure the HBC channel response. However, each of these instruments has its own characteristics, which must be considered in order to obtain a reliable channel characterization.

Measurements using Vector Network Analyzer

Vector Network Analyzer (VNA) is one of the most commonly tool used for characterization and

Fig.3 . Balanced winding terminals capacitances to ground (C_{bal1} and C_{bal2}) and interwinding capacitance (C_{iw}).

modeling of RF/microwave components and systems. It allows the accurate determination of reflection and transmission coefficients via measurement of S-parameters. For that reason, VNA is the preferred instrument to characterize and model the HBC channel. Nevertheless, a path exists between the internal grounds of the measurement ports of the VNA, leading to erroneous measurements. Therefore, a grounding strategy is

needed in order to avoid this undesired effect. In this regard, to improve the measurement of the HBC channel, it has been suggested to electrically isolate both the TX and RX electrodes from the common internal ground of the VNA using balanced-unbalanced (balun) devices [7], [8]. However, when baluns are used, different parasitic paths could appear, as illustrated in Fig. 2(a) for galvanic, and in Fig. 2(b) for capacitive HBC approach. This parasitic paths are associated to:

i) parasitic coupling path through the interwinding capacitance (C_{iw}), which inevitably occurs due to the physical proximity of primary and secondary coils inside the balun. As shown in Fig. 3, C_{iw} creates a parasitic path between the unbalanced to the balanced terminals of the balun, this allows the common mode signal to flow through the balun, affecting the measurement results.

ii) The asymmetrical capacitances between their “balanced” terminals and ground, illustrated in Fig. 3 as C_{bal1} and C_{bal2} . For a perfectly symmetrical balun, these capacitances should be equal in the whole frequency range, otherwise, this could influence the reference of the differential signal, affecting the integrity of the HBC channel and creating an unexpected return path via external environment.

It is necessary to consider both effects for a correct interpretation of the HBC channel characterization and modeling.

Fig.4 . Experimental setup using SG and SA for HBC channel characterization by. (a) Galvanic Method (b) Capacitive Method and (c) Magnetically-coupled Method.

Measurements using Signal Generators and Spectrum Analyzers or Oscilloscopes

When Signal Generators (SG) and Spectrum Analyzers (SA) or Oscilloscopes (OS) are used to characterize the HBC channel, the VNA internal cabled connection between TX and RX ground is avoided. Although this configuration splits the TX and RX to two different instruments, the channel integrity could still be affected by the ground connection of the equipment connected directly to the mains electricity supply. If they are battery powered this issue is avoided, however, the TX and RX ground plane is extended by the equipment's casing. As with the VNA, a solution is to use baluns in order to further isolate the grounds. With this approach, only parasitic paths to the earth ground via the instrument's ground will remain[9], as illustrated in Fig. 4(a) for the GHBC, being necessary to include this undesirable effects in order to get a correct model of the HBC channel.

In the case of the CHBC, illustrated in Fig. 4(b), when SG and SA are used with baluns, the independent ground of each instrument affects mainly the return path of the HBC channel. Then, for this coupling technique the separation of the instrument's ground does not necessarily represent a significant improvement in the HBC channel measurements in comparison with the case where a VNA is used to perform the experimental characterization.

Using the experimental setup based on SG and SA with baluns, the MHBC has been validated in [5]. For this coupling method, when the foot or hand detaches from the corresponding electrode the effective loop opens and the magnetic coupling disappear, interrupting the transmission, as illustrated in Fig. 4(c). Experimental results evidences that when the signal electrode is not in contact with the person, transmission through the body is not possible, as shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. MHBC experimental pathloss comparing open and close loop at receiver.

In the case of MHBC, the effective loop could be affected mainly by a parasitic path via the balun's interwinding capacitance C_{iw} , even when the transmission was established.

Measurements using battery powered transceivers

Custom battery powered transceivers can be used as TX and RX or with other desk equipment to characterize the HBC channel. When battery powered instruments are used, most of the parasitic couplings observed on laboratory equipment are eliminated. However, despite having small form factors when compared to desk instruments, they can still be bigger than most practical wearable devices, that are ideally equal or smaller than wristwatches. The size is usually a result of using off-the-shelf components and bulk batteries which creates coupling planes that must be accounted for. Also, the performance is usually limited, specially the required wide frequency ranges, dynamic range and sensitivity [8].

Devices/equipment impedances

Another important issue is related to the matching impedance of the devices used in the measurements. While VNAs present 50Ω matched ports, measurements using two separated instruments, a SG and OS, for instance, require to consider both the SG

Fig.6 . Capacitive coupling HBC primary channel with its (a) intrinsic and extrinsic parts and its (b) Extended model.

output impedance, usually 50Ω , as well as the input impedance of the OS, usually in the range of mega-ohms. This uneven impedance measure may considerably affect channel matching and gain for all coupling techniques and, therefore, should be carefully considered in the modeling of the HBC channel.

The same attention has to be taken for battery powered transceivers, since custom designs prefer to use non-standard input/output impedances to increase channel gain through matching [9].

Thus, to identify, analyze and properly account for the parasitics related to the test fixtures that affect the HBC measurements, a clear division between the measurement setup and the HBC channel composing parts is essential. In the next section we describe a modeling procedure presented in [10],[11] that proposes such division and is able to take into account the influence of the test fixture on the channel measurements. The method was specifically developed for CHBC, however a similar approach can be taken to measurements and modeling procedures for GHBC or MHBC.

Equivalent Circuit Model for CHBC channel measurement interpretation

The development of a proper Capacitive HBC channel model that is able to predict the correct channel behavior, even when the measurements are performed with laboratory equipment and accessories, needs, before anything else, a clear definition of the basic, or primary, HBC channel, that

does not account for the measurement setup. In this regard, in [11], the CHBC primary channel is divided into an intrinsic and an extrinsic part, detailed below:

i) The intrinsic part is the direct path through the body between the signal electrodes, as shown in Fig. 6(a), which is modeled by the electrical properties of the tissues. This intrinsic part is considered static, since it does not change with the external conditions, being only dependent on the distance of propagation over the body.

ii) The extrinsic part is constituted by the return path through the environment between the external ground plane and the ground electrodes, including alternative signal paths that would probably be seen in the real channel, as signal leakage directly from the body to the electrodes or the ground. The interfaces between the transceivers and the body, i.e., the electrodes, are considered also parts of the extrinsic channel, as shown in Fig. 6(a). The extrinsic portion of the channel is dependent mostly on the external characteristics, the distance from the ground, the presence of objects in the return path, and the electrodes and their contact with the skin.

Once the effects present in the primary HBC channel are adequately established and differentiated, the potential influences of the measurement setup on the channel should be identified. From Fig 6(a), for measurements employing a VNA, baluns and coaxial cables, these influences are: the instrument-to-ground coupling, the interwinding capacitances of the baluns, and the cables transitions that make the contact with the

electrodes.

A model created using both the primary channel and the measurement setup influences described above is called an extended CHBC model, and captures the test fixture influences on the channel measurement results. A practical alternative to describe the propagation characteristics of the extended CHBC is to use an equivalent circuit model. This kind of model is more intuitive and practical than theoretical electromagnetic or 3-D numerical simulation model, that even with simplifications are very complex to be solved.

In Fig. 6(b), the circuit diagram shows the extended model proposed in [11] that includes the essential components to reproduce the extended channel behavior. The intrinsic channel is represented by C_{body} and R_{body} , which here only exemplify a lumped or distributed model for the body tissues [11]. The extrinsic channel part comprises C_e , which models the interelectrode capacitance; C_{ret} , which models the transceiver ground electrode coupling to the external ground in and other parasites appearing through the environment; C_x , which models the direct cross coupling between the ground electrodes from the transmitter and the receiver; and C_{leak} , which is the leakage capacitance that represents each unit length body segment coupling to the external ground. The remaining components are related to the test fixture modeling: L_m , which represents the magnetizing inductance of the balun; C_t and L_t takes into account the electrical transition coaxial-to-PCB; L_l and R_l , considers the balun flux leakage.

This extended model achieved good results regarding the channel gain and frequency profiles up to 70 MHz, as shown in Fig.7. Additionally, it provides a clear division of the primary HBC channel into two parts, intrinsic and extrinsic, aiding in the identification and modeling of the essential channel components using distributed and lumped circuit representations which, despite being simple, provided useful insights into the expected HBC channel behavior.

Fig 7. Measurement and model simulation results for CHBC channel [11].

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